

ISic3019

I.Sicily inscription 3019

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

rock

face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2013.10.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Buscemi

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 50161

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332329

1. [— —] ἐπὶ πα [ρά(?)]
2. Παιδέσσι καὶ [Ἄννα(?)]
3. ἀμ[φ]ιπόλου [— — — —]
4. ἐπὶ Ἄνῖα τοῦ [— — — —]
5. ΛΑC [— — — — — — — —]
6. ἱερίας δὲ T CY. .ΛΑC
7. [— — — — —]M [— — —]
8. [οἱ παραγενόμε]νοι
9. [ποτὶ Νύμφας(?) μ]ηνὸς
10. [— — — — — — — — — —]
11. ΟΤ □ Υ — — Δ
- 12.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645376

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Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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Manganaro, G. 1992. Iscrizioni "rupestri" di Sicilia. In Gasperini, L.(eds.), *Rupes loquentes: atti del convegno internazionale di studio sulle iscrizioni rupestri di età romana in Italia. Roma - Bomarzo 13-15.X.1989*. Rome. pp. 447-501. At 464 no.6

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